

THE NOTION OF ETHICS FORMED FROM STIGMA DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10511670**Andressa Loss Guimarães**

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the theme 'ethics formed from stigmas'. Its scientific relevance applies to the fact that it contributes to science by having a more characteristic direction in the training of professionals who intend to work in the areas of human and social sciences. Its social relevance lies in the fact that it can help to, if not resolve, at least reduce the contingency of abuses and the creation of values without the slightest criteria. Its relevance to the human sciences lies in aspects linked to in-depth studies of human thought, especially the unconscious and how ethics can be worked on as a form of growth for human beings. This is a bibliographical, analytical research, based on social thought and philosophical development. With the creation of Psychoanalysis, analyzes about the human experience with peers and its nuances with the supernatural became more susceptible to questioning about becoming and what one is and why it is not otherwise. The constructs of morality as a doctrine lead human beings to an inner conflict that manifests itself in actions that can never be explained in the light of another science, without its support. What emerges, as a broader discussion, is how the human being was able to create something that diminished himself in the face of the cosmos?

Keywords: Ethics. Stigma. Society. Individual and collective thinking.

INTRODUCTION

Ethics, contrary to what is commonly thought and translated, is not a tangible element that can be manipulated without a high social and individual cost. Like every action that depends on maintenance and effects to survive, it suffers pressure from social stigmas that, once internalized by individuals, transform into true cancerous structures that are never cured, rather cushioned by palliative effect drugs that cause more damage than normal. disease itself. The point of addressing this situation even in the presentation of the text is that sociological problems are always complex, due to the fact that it involves, in addition to many elements, many ways of interpreting it, having as influence culture, the mechanism of family creation , the experiences lived in the most diverse environments and how much they all impacted on the individual's thinking.

Ethics is an expression of behavior and, in this way, it needs elements that justify it, since, without an explanation [*or without a justification*] for certain acts, interpreted as disproportionate that are practiced against special groups, society would revolt and I wouldn't accept them. Clemency and even exclusion or social dismissal depend on being understood by the collective regarding their application and the reasons must be convincing; not just fair, given that we are faced with another concept that is too abstract to be accepted without a criterion of value.

Throughout history, many instruments and conditions that were used to determine order and morality in societies ended up being banned and never allowed to be practiced again because of the hidden and unethical objectives they had in their determinations. In the name of noble ideals, humans sacrifice all honor and dignity [*of others*]; they practice all types of abuse and symbolic violence; they create conjectures, myths, they use individual experience, which is nothing more than the application of personal paranoia on a collective, in order to gain followers for the application of sadistic and psychopathic feelings and this works, very effectively, until the group understands how they are being manipulated and deceived by that supposed expert, gifted with vision beyond their reach.

This is where the issue of ethics and its application become objects of study and understanding, because its interest is in respect to laws, customs and, by extension, the maintenance of order and social well-being. When, in its name, this is not perceived, with only privileges remaining for a few, what we have is a tyrannical state installed that breaks the entire balance, leading *Physis itself* to develop protection mechanisms against such attacks. The values of a human being can only be measured based on their coexistence in an environment where

there are others and for which the existence of principles that must be respected is preserved. When someone breaks with such orders, there is a fission in the structure of the system and the entire chain goes into a state of alert, potentially leading to collapse and imminent chaos.

In order to maintain control, groups were created upon which all kinds of evil were targeted, causing society to become disordered, imposing on them a symbolic mark, a stigma that they carry, even if they are not responsible. directly by social misfortunes. It turns out that, once people believe that they are, directing combat actions and responses become faster, preventing the spread of panic among the population. This is a special type of ethical construction implemented in democratic systems, where imaginary figures are created that resist general social well-being, becoming anarchists and, consequently, provoking terror.

It must be understood that the social constructions that act on ethics are formed and consolidated based on the customs of a given society, which allows us to reach the obvious conclusion that an individual left to his own devices could never be judged as ethical or no, because it lacks the other as a judging element, which would have the function of ensuring that such a situation is consolidated. Therefore, it always expresses a conception of man and society that is born, grows and is guided from the direction and extent of the relationships that are maintained between individuals (SOUZA, 2012).

Understanding this thought allows us to say that healthy environments based on relationships where conflicts are not avoided, but rather are treated with the deference that is due to them, end up generating individuals who respect each other based on their sets of ideas, determinations and convictions, without May this deliberately turn your neighbor into your enemy. But, in contemporary society, political governance is unthinkable without a state of deliberate chaos and, for this, it is necessary to create a monster, name it and impose on its body an image that reveals all its Machiavellian intentions and, from a young age, all citizens are trained to flee when faced with that symbol, which denotes that the being itself is nearby. This state of collective paranoid fear means that the State no longer has control over the object of horror; but, on a larger scale, on law-abiding citizens, concerned about their personal safety and that of their loved ones.

A psychological situation is created that cannot be understood by the individual dominated by sociological thinking, because at the same time that an *I was created*, starting with Renè Descartes (1181-1235 dH) in the opposite direction of a *we*, they had to do hard work of transforming this being into a eunuch, through the implementation of a contagious and depraved disease in his spirit and which, later on, formal education would ensure its

dissemination: namely, guilt , for being free and not interested in being part of the flock commanded by a priest.

Therefore, the group superimposed as the target element of social hatred needs to be described and understood in this way, the target object of horror for everyone, kept under intense stigmatization, because otherwise, the whole process ends in negative results, which means, remaining outside of state control. It is through this mechanism that ethics formed from stigmas is produced and reproduced, which is neither common nor individual behavior; it is collective, universalized through an instrument directed by the State.

Political propaganda for the well-being and protection of ordinary citizens requires the existence of a trained monster that has been created in your image and likeness, because all you need to do is analyze your own feelings and you will know how to act to invalidate your opponent. The situation worsens and expands to such a point that entire ghettos begin to emerge living under stigma, areas where it is said that there is low state status, that is, everyone who lives there starts to carry the same cursed mark, as if it were imposed by such a form in their DNA, that not even the extraction of the individual from such a space can erase it and, once exposed, their entire state of being is revealed through social value judgments.

Ethics suffers pressure from all fields, because it can be considered as a pragmatic force, therefore, it automatically becomes subject to manipulation and the object of the ideological apparatuses of the State and dominant forces, as necessary. Although,

No universal ethics will be possible without properly intersubjective relationships, especially those established in the order of reciprocity between rights and duties, and which are intertwined between individuals of an intended universal civilization, being lived and recognized as ethical relationships, becoming legitimized. objectively, that is, publicly as an expression of an ethical community (VAZ, 1991, p. 07).

It is understood from this statement that the denominations that receive the infinite stamps created by the demagogues on duty cannot be defined and accepted as ethical, simply for the fact of receiving such a nickname, considering that, when stereotypes are created about a certain category of individuals or situation, stigmas are created together which, due to the misfortune of their enemies, once labeled by the social concept, end up as victims of a sophistry that accompanies them throughout the existence of humanity, since not even death is capable of breaking through such a situation.

All of this just reiterates the idea that ethics produced from stigmas is a control apparatus, very strategic and that it should be considered as such, not because it has strength in itself; but, due to the fact that it makes it possible to organize the process of social coexistence,

always guided by the fear of being, in some way, stigmatized and, as a consequence of this, being condemned to live on the margins of everything and everyone, without many chances of a place in the sun in society.

ETHICAL CONCEPTS

Every object of study, before advancing on it and even allowing a broad and deep understanding of itself, needs to be clarified regarding its semantic and social meaning. So, what is ethics? This is a question that may seem to convey an obvious answer; but, the closer you get to an interpretation, the more clear it becomes that its meaning contains countless elements that cannot be interpreted randomly. For some, ethics represents a set of moral values developed by each culture, with the purpose of governing the principles of each society. And it couldn't be any other way. Ethics is present in all human groups. It is a set of rules, principles or way of thinking and expressing. It is a word of Greek origin with two [possible] translations: custom and property of character.

But what exactly does ethics mean? According to the Aurélio Eletrônico Dictionary (2015, p. 57), ethics means “the study of judgments regarding human conduct capable of being qualified from the point of view of good and evil, whether in relation to a given society or absolutely” .

This definition given to the word places it as a dubious and intransigent element, because nothing, in nature, can be relative or absolute, at the same time and, in the case of something that represents the way of maintaining the social order, it is clear that its value is absolute and anyone who departs from the determinations, of all existing nature, is already in violation of respect for ethical standards.

Etymologically, the word ethics (*ethos*) is a transliteration of two Greek words: $\eta\theta o\zeta$ (*ethos*) which means man's home, animal's home: lair, cave, $\eta\theta o\zeta$ which gives the sense of protective shelter, man finds a lifestyle and action in the space of the world. Get used to your home. Hence the custom, but this address is capable of perfectibility, of perfection. The other word $\epsilon\theta o\zeta$ (*ethos*) means behavior that results from repeating the same acts - a constant that manifests custom, the individual's act - there is habit. Both customs and habits are constructed, that is, they are artificial elements that, at some point before, were not present in culture and that, in the same way, can lose their value and meaning of existence, for reasons beyond everyone's control. Cultural dynamism is a factor that cannot be controlled in a rigorous and

excessive manner; which causes mechanisms to emerge to protect beliefs and laws, transforming them into objects of tradition.

With the creation of Psychoanalysis, analyzes about the human experience with peers and its nuances with the supernatural became more susceptible to questioning about becoming and what one is and why it is not otherwise. The constructs of morality as a doctrine lead human beings to an inner conflict that manifests itself in actions that can never be explained in the light of another science, without its support. It [*Ethics*] is the judge of morals, since it is formed in the human unconscious, which makes it, thus, a kind of legislation of social Moral behavior, functioning as a *Procrustus' Bed*¹, seeking to find a fair measure for the individual. And, the complexity increases because being a free man, he is free to accept his principles as well as to ignore them.

Much has been confused between the fact that freedom has been gained to question the motives of various elements of value existing in society and their meaning with unrestricted disobedience to these dictates. Thought develops in proportion to the fact that it and all the objects that provoked its reaction are placed under doubt and criticized, which is far from saying that they can be subjected to the taste of individual insult, and that any change in behavior must be the target of resistance, when it emerged, in order to preserve the doctrine and have a minimum of security regarding the present and the future.

Jean-Jacques Rousseau (1712-1778) wrote in his work *confessions* that, if freedom consisted in doing everything one wants, no man could ever consider himself free. He could not have stated a more serious thing because, by allowing volitional deliberation without the slightest rules, he would be condemned to a system of slavery and, by the way, the most bloodthirsty that exists, considering that it acts as a silent and imperative force, transforming into an addiction that needs to be fed at all times.

Taking this thought as a reference point for interpretation, ethics also exists to enable human beings to find their state of happiness, because when they balance the forces of impulsive individual desire and what the collective takes to be ideal, they have if remaining in a state of situational control in which punishment is not necessary as a way of returning the state of things to normality.

¹ *Procrustes* was a thief who lived by robbing anyone who passed by on the road that connected Megara to Athens. Only those who were going through a terrible trial could cross his path: the bandit had an iron bed of his exact size, not an inch more or less, where he made his victim lie down. If the person was larger than the bed, their legs were amputated; if they were smaller, they were stretched until they reached the desired size. This horror only ended when the hero Theseus did to him what he always did to his victims, he placed him on the bed, but a little to the side, leaving the head and feet that were amputated by the hero. Thief, in the time of Theseus, was the name for someone who was a hunter.

Every time state forces need to take action in order to resolve collective disagreements, someone has broken the social contract and, even if such actions are as routine or even more routine than the very existence of the control law, they demonstrate that man, in the absence of coercive power, becomes a primitive beast, given that his personal interests speak louder than collective interests.

So, when someone drastically breaks the rules of coexistence, punishment is demanded, partly out of fear and partly motivated by envy for not having the same courage demonstrated by the transgressor of the established order. A reading of the myths demonstrates how much the hero's audacity and courage were exalted in times of war and, paradoxically, were condemned in times of peace. Nothing has changed in the social interpretation of the thing itself and the stigmas inferred on the warrior during the battle, which lead him to the *status quo* of hero, are transmuted into serious offenses, transforming him into a match. The situation determines who will be defined as the hero or the villain. This is how social ethics works, creating and imposing stigmas according to the political interests of the moment.

ETHICS AS A PRAGMATIC PRINCIPLE

Ethics, by itself, does not create or stipulate principles or paradigms. It is society that, through its leaders, creates doctrines and forces everyone to follow such and such dictated values as if they were canonical rules. There is always someone who will not agree with them and will rise up against them. These are those who will be stigmatized by the group they lead. In fact, it is always pertinent that someone rebels automatically and autonomously; this exempts the dominant from creating such stereotypes. Because every theory without its opposite becomes meaningless. Most of the time, stigmatized people are as much to blame for their condition as a stone is for being a stone.

Sigmund Freud's theory about the unconscious and its faulty acts contributed to creating a more balanced moral and ethical conduct. He himself was already questioning the repercussions that his theory would cause in the moral discourse of his time by displacing the conscious subject from its dominant position in the psyche. This "severe blow to the universal narcissism of men" (Freud, 1917, p. 149) did not fail to produce effects in various fields of human activity: affirming that the self is no longer the master of its own house implied rethinking and redefining an entire way of thinking, whose Enlightenment heritage centered the human will in the field of consciousness (ANDRADE JÚNIOR, 2007).

Contrary to what is commonly believed, perhaps due to ignorance and/or self-indulgence, stigmatizing labels do not fall heavily on an isolated individual and end there. Stigma takes care of generalizing the concept about a certain class, at the same time that it disseminates and builds an entire structure so that whoever is a member of the group cannot escape unscathed from the ideology constructed, disseminated and applied. In the era of abstraction, a brand is always a symbol, a signifier and its meaning depends on whoever recognizes it in any way, a family name, geographic descent, academic training, participation in some notable event; in other words, the mark that was imposed on the condemned, in Greece, became the result of the trauma caused by the experience itself.

The intellectual decadence that contemporary society is experiencing has favored the misinterpretation of the concept of ethics and even more so its pragmatic application to life and existence, in which judgments cannot be made to the detriment of some sacrificant who is repeating what everyone wants to hear and take it as absolute truth. Society continues to create its stigmatized elements, however, with more care when exposing them, because there is a whole movement to transform such creatures into victims of circumstances and who, under favorable conditions, *can* become perfect individuals in insane worlds.

It turns out that ethics is not a solution to any social problem; Carnious environments require behaviors to the same extent and what is portrayed as waves of barbarism and insanity can thus be interpreted in distant locations and, hypothetically, free from such investitures. The moral values that are taught at school do not adapt to life in all its spaces and situations, which means that the majority do not understand certain actions taken by managers and leaders when in open confrontation against groups that act under another way of thinking. and ethical determination.

According to Goffman (1963)

The Greeks created the term stigma to refer to bodily signs that sought to highlight something extraordinary or bad about the moral *status* of the person presenting them. The signs were made with cuts or fire on the body and warned that the bearer was a slave, a criminal or a traitor, *that is*, a marked person, ritually polluted, who should be avoided; especially in public places (Id., p. 5). (Our emphasis)

Currently, due to the imperialism of Christianity and its ideologies, this condition has fallen on a class in particular: prisoners. Based on concepts of individuals who suffered from incurable guilt for their endless crimes, they created concepts of classifications for individuals who should be avoided because they incurred *hybris*, that is, they violated social ethics in such a way that they should be avoided, not only because of physical damage that they can cause to

others, but because such a condition of moral inferiority is subject to imminent contagion and once infected, there is no cure, because being intangible in nature, there is no way to extract a feeling from the whole. Once the individual has been tried and convicted before a popular jury, that is, composed of his equals, and, having served his prescribed sentence in full, he should be considered free from any guilt and exempt from popular judgment by his peers. .

However, this is not how the situation presents itself and a judgment of value and exclusion is imposed on the individual, causing them to remain excluded from any type of opportunity that society can offer them. His sentence and subsequent condemnation become a stigma that needs to be kept hidden from everyone's knowledge, without distinction, because a kind of unconscious and ferocious fear dominates everyone, something as if that being was always ready to attack without any reason. make it presumptive.

This leads to the deduction that social ethics is formed by and through fear, the worst advisor that man can take for himself and, over time, the education aimed at younger people becomes based on these terms, causing the vicious cycle of social exclusion promoted by paranoid and unhealthy fear is the most plausible explanation [*if not, a powerful justification*] for the most insane and excessive acts to be practiced, in the name of justice, morality and social well-being. In such a way that it ended up becoming a tool of manipulation in the hands of a few and that, not infrequently, the social uprising against these positions is what allows a little light to be shed on the discernments taken as being within standards of the ethic.

What we have is that ethics can be applied to any social instance; however, in democratic regimes it follows a more sophisticated and refined standard of service to citizens, because everyone, equally, is imbued with public rights and duties, considering that when one party demands their rights, the other finds themselves on the verge of serving them. them, since it is an obligation of their constitutional duty. Therefore, respect for constitutional precepts represents the ethical principles to be followed by the population, even if they do not agree, and there is a free right to question and fight to change them, making them more flexible or more rigid, according to the popular will and the sequence of crimes that we intend to combat.

In a psychoanalytic view, ethics acts like an organism that, paradoxically, causes discomfort and joy to the individual. Discomfort because it is a judge who forces a stance, a rigidity that goes against human beings' instincts for freedom of action, restricting them, limiting them, castrating them. It provides joy because the same individual who desires freedom at all costs, wishes to be accepted as a member of a group and, respecting the principles imposed by his peers, remains a member of a certain social group of his preference. This is not a gregarious feeling, but an instinctive need for protection/security that only group cohesion can

guarantee. Understanding here, a neurotic fear of death that isolation could cause in remote times in the prehistory of the human species. However, for the group to also survive together, it was necessary to have order, strict laws of conduct.

When any member of the group breaks with the established natural order, they must quickly be punished with all the rigor of the law and, in an excessive manner, disproportionate to the crime committed, not because they deserve it; rather, because the idea is to curb the latent intention that pulses in other people's thoughts. Man only obeys social rules and remains ethical through fear, which is not a condition he adopts naturally; At certain times you need to be reminded of what could happen to you if you do not take due care with your moral stance. The public condemnations and the resulting executions initially had this idea; but they very easily became delirious spectacles in which spectators became entranced by the horror *show and, paradoxically, no longer felt aversion to the scenes.*

This feeling of indifference in the face of the most bizarre and cruel situations is a type of ethics that is formed in the personological condition of individuals as they are constantly subjected to degrading situations, repeatedly. Many are mistaken in thinking that ethics refers exclusively to good behavior or concern for the well-being of others. If its semantic concept is *behavior*, it requires that each individual behave according to the situation itself, in order to be considered ethical and, in many cases, when taking a stance against certain situations and stigmas, it is that they are acting in the opposite direction to the ethical precepts of that group in which it is inserted. When you see yourself as part of a collective, your moral obligation is to follow the rules dictated by it, even if you don't agree with any of them.

SOCIAL ETHICS IN RELATION TO INDIVIDUALS TEMPORARILY DEPRIVED OF PHYSICAL FREEDOM

Since severe laws of conduct were being imposed on individuals under the auspices of a certain group, those who broke such rules received a sanction that, in ancient times, was capital punishment. This is because the action of one individual put the entire community at risk; therefore, his sentence should serve as an example so that others would not dare to follow him in his delinquent enterprise. The sanction served to admonish those spirits with a desire for rebellion and, thus, public order was maintained.

As time went by, human beings became more sadistic and sublimated their sadism under the concept of justice. The offender who was eliminated in time began to be exposed, with the aim of atoning for his crime and awakening terror in other citizens, having his conditions of

freedom and action limited to a mediocre space; once condemned to death by starvation in fetid cellars and dungeons. But, with the advent of the refinement of social laws, they began to be placed in cells, containing little space and their names were exposed to then suffer a moral condemnation that leads everyone to perpetual marginalization; once sanctioned, forever condemned.

No one, not even an individual who is imprisoned, that is, temporarily deprived of freedom, can be subjected to inhumane living conditions by any other citizen. There is no psychological or sociological parameter that justifies such attitudes; even because 35% of men and 60% of women arrested in the country are behind bars for small, irrelevant, almost ridiculous crimes, such as the theft of some nonsense in a supermarket or a gas cylinder or a chicken in a residence. And also for smaller actions, without blood or death, in drug trafficking. Cheap steam, rocket launcher, lookout, that sort of thing. This group could perfectly well be punished outside of prisons, with alternative sentences combined with the obligation to carry out social work, such as, for example, providing services to charitable institutions. But, in a very subtle way, the offender is punished, because in human subjectivity there is a need to have its scourge crushed and, therefore, prevented from manifesting itself. It is clear that human education is still based on violence and the expression of pain. Imposing pain on a social peer is a way of awakening the pathetic in the community and preventing it from becoming the next victim of the same fateful fate as the contemporary scapegoat.

There are many theories to explain what causes crime. Each of them applies perfectly to at least one criminal situation, but none can explain the origin of all crimes. According to Soares (2006),

'Crime' is a very broad concept. There is no general theory about crime because there is no 'general' crime. When we talk about crime, we are referring to the transgression of a law, and this encompasses an infinite number of different situations, each favored by certain conditions (Id., p. 12).

Crime is an action that harms social balance, since artificial values are consequences of temporality and defined constructions, being linked to a specific purpose aimed at maintaining the order established *a priori*. However, the most interesting thing is that even though the criminal action can be seen and understood as a stigma, what becomes such is the prison and not the conviction itself, a strange paradox with which society has been taught to live and to take as an [*almost*] absolute truth; a presumption perhaps motivated by the epigenetic transformation that affects the individual, once deprived of their freedom.

Serving your sentence in a closed regime, that is, spending time in prison, is the mark from which you can no longer escape, becoming an eternal condemned person and doomed to

unprecedented ostracism. You are not here to judge the morals of anyone; What we seek to discuss are the determining variables of human existence in society, which are very complex in terms of the treatment given to each situation, in particular, and not to individuals, in a generic way.

Suddenly, someone's life transforms in such a way that everything they have achieved in years of existence disappears under a moral prejudice, called ethics and determined by an intriguing way of interpreting and understanding the nature of things. Society lives on labels and, if someone is not capable of being labeled, this is the first step towards being stigmatized, another paradox, because the semantic meaning of both words are marks imposed on individuals, in such a way that, in this way, way you can recognize them. What the Greeks did with criminals was a way in which the one who had been marked could be the target of attacks by those who were sadistic to the point of being at the same level of misery as him, because the simple fact of seeing such a figure already stained, requiring heavy purification rituals. Nothing different from what happens today; in which the simple presence of someone stigmatized by social ethics already causes everyone to move away under the allegation of feeling bad and marked by a strange and frightening presence.

Social ethics is governed by superstitions and, no matter how much we want to abolish the idea of individuals, the strength that comes from the collective is still much superior and, in the end, what we have is more of a belief, arising from opinions, from that all this feeling is transmitted to men through culture itself; which is a half-truth, when what you have is education playing this role in a very perfect way, so well schematized that any preconception against a certain group becomes something subjective; so much so that if you ask someone why they feel aversion to these individuals, you won't know how to argue or even give a reason. Stigma becomes a specific condition, created and sustained in the interest of everyone avoiding it, in a Spartan way: don't get caught!

CONCLUSION

The creation of Psychoanalysis and the discovery of the unconscious as a unit of human thought that could be studied systematically, by Sigmund Freud, led to an intense change in the structure of interpretation of ethical and moral values constructed by society. This creates a range of actions that stigmatize a class, a collective, because they are different or because they do not fit into what the masses consider to be an ideal model of behavior.

From studies on failed acts and unforeseen behaviors, much has opened up as a mechanism of understanding for certain human actions, previously not understood and treated as madness or even planned insanity. However, all this control over individual and collective attitudes did not prove to be enough to remove from the masses the concepts arising from common sense about human beings themselves and the construction of stigmas that kept everyone under strict and rigorous control.

What becomes very transparent in the study of ethics, in relation to the behavior of the masses, is that they need something to identify with in relation to their object of valuation-depreciation, and it is not possible to live with something that is different to them without providing it. a label, which becomes a special type of power, a Machiavellian identification that imposes on its recipient a condition of submission from which they can never escape.

Many situations that humans are subjected to or that they are forced to go through, voluntarily or not [*most of them are accidental*], leave consequences that make them react in a strange way to the situation they are experiencing and that are reflections of moments in which they left violent traumas in their personalities, which arouses fear in the participants because they are unaware of the reactions of individuals who have been subjected to torturous conditions and a high degree of stress, which causes the appearance of strange behaviors, unconventional to formal means of experience and social coexistence.

In a very natural way, if human beings are left to their desires and insanity, without a special type of control, in a short time they transform into something monstrous, uncontrollable and, it is exactly for this reason that ethics emerges in living spaces. human, as a mechanism capable of maintaining balance between order and chaos; not to rule existence and limit life to determinisms created in offices by some demagogue.

The Greeks created stigmata to determine special types of criminals, one of which, in which Aristotle says, would apply to pedophiles, child sexual aggressors. In Iraq, when captured, thieves are branded with a hot iron on their foreheads so that everyone knows their crime and, in the accounts in the book of Genesis, it is said that Cain received a brand for having murdered his youngest brother, Abel, which shows that the custom of stigmatizing criminal agents, in human history, is longstanding. Nowadays, with all the apparatus of human rights and the guarantee of the *dignity of the human person* , as a fundamental clause of international law, such behaviors are unacceptable, as was the case of the teenager in São Paulo who had derogatory sayings tattooed on his forehead.

In order to keep themselves under control, human beings created laws, sometimes absurd and cruel, against anyone who committed an act of *disproportionateness*, guaranteeing,

in this way, the maintenance of order, which would be the conscious manifestation of the desire, however, deep within each being, hidden from everyone's sight, is the desire to keep an insane beast under control that has not become accustomed to a peaceful and devout life.

Naturally, the human being is a wild creature with no defined limits for others like him; respecting only the dictates of a greater force to those who fear, as they are unaware of its mood and how it will punish it; almost always failing to escape their deadly furies unharmed, which led him to elect them as sovereign gods, impossible to control. In this way, these beings cannot have their behavior determined by social rules created, artificially, by man, which makes him angry and, in many moments, there were priests who burped that they had such control, which meant that the population did not fear the chthonic forces more than their lords. This feeling is still very present in the Contemporary Era through the behavior of unscrupulous religious people who emerge, not because they are simply sacrilegious; but, because the human being, in a certain way, needs to be in front of a powerful being to such an extent that he even controls the destiny and behavior of everything that exists in nature, that is, someone who is feared and obeyed even by the Creator himself.

When someone assumes such power and becomes revered by the faithful, creating social stigmas becomes the easiest thing, because ethics start to be determined by him and not by a set of values that society considers ideal, after a heavy conflict of interests and discussions. The problem with stigma is that, once established, it never ends, making it almost impossible to eliminate it from the popular unconscious. In a short time, it becomes natural law and summary trials begin to occur in all sectors without the accused being able to provide the minimum conditions of defense. Of course, an entire mechanism of self-depreciation was built and made available to humans, so that when subjected to the rigors of canon law they would not question it and the cultural-educational system took good care to program everyone, without distinction, to internalize such feeling, making it a common place in society. Once this feat was achieved, nothing else that was considered ethical was questioned by the masses and anyone who dared to do so was already treated as a subversive and anarchist; therefore, unethical.

And such consideration already becomes a stigma, where wherever one goes, this individual is seen as someone who breaks with the cosmic order, capable of bringing more omens and thus awakening the wrath of some god on everyone; that is, it should be avoided; if not, deleted. In the name of ethics, anything can be done, even what is considered unethical in formal discourse; but experience shows that it is completely the opposite.

Along with the creation of ethics, guilt was created, which combined with educational processes produces the ideal man for society. This follows pre-established standards and at the

same time remains within the mold, becoming an example to be followed. Perhaps it is here, exactly, at this point of convergence between the hairy beast and the polished man that neuroses arise, understanding that Freud interpreted them as an expression of forms of sublimated moral conflicts.

But, there is a question: why would man create something that would be capable of castrating him? Therefore, if such a process was conscious, the desire was not that of a mass; but, of a single individual, in which, to meet the collective's desires for a strong leader, he showed himself as such and at the same time, created a condition in which all others were transformed into eunuchs. From this, it follows that his power does not come from his strength; but, from the weakness of others, from submission to this belief.

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